

THE STRATEGIES FOR ENHANCING CITIZEN ENGAGEMENT AND PARTICIPATION IN LOCAL GOVERNANCE AND PUBLIC POLICY

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Introduction:

India is a world's largest democratic country, where adopted parliamentary system to elect representatives through free and fair elections. 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment acts of 1992 gave birth to local self-governments as panchayats at village level and municipalities at city level through inclusion their essentiality in Constitution of India to achieve the aim of upholding the gross root democracy. After more than 30 years of implementation, it's the time to evaluate whether LSG - local self-governments made any impact on rural livelihood and achieved welfare of the citizen or not.

Key Words : *Governance, Participation, Democracy and Development.*

The Ways of Citizen Engagement and Participation in Local Governance and Public Policy:

- ▶ **Through Voting** – Under universal adult franchise, the citizen who aged 18 years and above are eligible to cast their vote in LSG's elections.
- ▶ **Contesting in Election** – Under 73rd and 74th constitutional amendment acts, the citizen who aged 21 years and above are eligible to contest particular elections of LSG's.
- ▶ **Requisition to LSG's** – The citizens can request various services and other related matters through regular meetings of GramSabhas and Wards.
- ▶ **Critique to Government** – The citizens are empowered to question to LSG's on matters related to particular Panchayats or Municipalities and get better solutions.

- ▶ **Public Opinion** – The citizens can give their opinions in policy, programme or scheme matters for the effective implementation of them and to reach people effectively.
- ▶ **Applying Various Schemes of Government** – People can apply for various government schemes through LSG's and get benefitted the same. For example: MGNREGA – Guarantees minimum employment from the government to unskilled labours of the rural areas.

Issues and Problems of Citizen Engagement and Participation in Local Governance and Public Policy:

- ▶ **Lack of Transparency** – As per CAG reports – 2024, 50% to 60% of the panchayats and Municipalities of many states, facing transparency issues in implementation of various programmes, schemes of the government and there is lacuna of maintaining the audit reports.
- ▶ **Lack of Efficiency** – NITI Aayog in its various reports, also highlighted the efficiency issues of LSG's and urged the state governments to rectify the matter and reform the policy implementation matters on urgent basis.
- ▶ **Lack of Accountability** – Though LSG's are gross roots of democracy, should accountable to people in their policy matters, implementation of programmes and every action of it.
- ▶ **Fake Promises** – During LSG's elections the contestants present the fake promises before the voters and grab the votes from them and after the winning elections they neglect their promises, when they presented during the elections.
- ▶ **Family Politics** – It is the one of major political evil which dominating the India's local governance. Members of same political family will contest various form of elections and indulge in power politics and not allowing any outsider from their family to get the political power.
- ▶ **Caste Politics** – Various media reports are showing that, the dominant castes are grabbing presidential positions in local governance of Panchayats and Municipalities through their money, muscle and appeasement of other backward classes.

These issues are badly impacted and resulted in lower voter turn outs in elections, here we understand the comparison of national, state and local level elections through following tables.

1. Lower Voter Turnout at National Level: Lok Sabha Elections:

SI. No.	Year of the Lok Sabha	Voting Turnout (%)
1	2004	58.07%
2	2009	58.91%
3	2014	66.44%
4	2019	67.40%
5	2024	66.33%

Source: <https://eci.gov.in>

2. Lower Voter Turnout at State Level: Karnataka Vidhan Sabha Elections:

SI. No.	Karnataka Vidhana Sabha Elections	Voting Turnout (%)
1	2003	65.00%
2	2008	64.68%
3	2013	71.83%
4	2018	72.50%
5	2023	73.84%

Source: <https://eci.gov.in>

3. Lower Voter Turnout at Local Level: Latest Panchayat Elections in India:

SI. No.	Year of Panchayat Election and State	Voting Turnout (%)
1	2021 – Andhra Pradesh	81.78%
2	2022 – Madhya Pradesh	80.31%
3	2023 – West Bengal	80.71%
4	2024 – Punjab	77%
5	2025 – Chhattisgarh	75.86%

Source: <https://eci.gov.in>

Recommended Strategies for Enhancing Citizen Engagement and Participation in Local Governance:

- ▶ **Quality Education** – As per the 2011 Census, the literacy rate in India was 74.04% and 25.96% of people were illiterate and doesn't know the reading and writing properly, most of them belongs rural areas. As politics concern qualitative and moral education is required to enhance the citizen engagement and participation in local governance.
- ▶ **Awareness** – There is a lack of awareness about the political system, government machinery and public administration among the people of rural areas. It must be addressed as a priority by the government, NGO's and other social groups by providing them proper political awareness.
- ▶ **Compulsory Voting** – More than 22 nations of the world are adopting voting as a compulsory duty of the citizen. For example: Australia, Belgium, Brazil, Egypt etc. As per as local governance concerned, in India voting should made a compulsory at local level to enhance the citizen engagement in local governance effectively.
- ▶ **Penalty and Punishments** – As per failure to voting is concern, there shall be penalizing provision should be made and through penalties and punishments, the government shall try to enhance the citizen engagement at local level.
- ▶ **Recall** – It is the reformative strategy adopted by few countries namely; Peru, Ecuador and Japan etc. In India states like Uttar Pradesh, Uttarakhand, Maharashtra are adopted the right to recall the representatives at Panchayati level. This should be implemented all India level to enhance the people participation efficiently.

Way Forward:

We are responsible to create better India for the future generation. People participation is the driving force of the democracy which needs continuous, active interest and participation by the people. As per local governance is concerned the citizen engagement in gross root politics is more essential phenomena, we should achieve this as a priority.

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